

Respiratory Distress syndrome in Full Term Neonates in the First Week of Life in Thi-Qar Province

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Abstract

Background: Respiratory distress in full-term neonates during the first week of life is a critical clinical issue, often manifesting as tachypnea, grunting, and retractions. Although typically associated with preterm births, full-term neonates also experience respiratory distress due to conditions like Transient Tachypnea of the Newborn (TTN), meconium aspiration syndrome, and infections. **Aim:** This study aimed to assess the causes, outcomes, and associated maternal, neonatal, and delivery characteristics of respiratory distress in full-term neonates admitted to neonatal care units in Thi-Qar Province. **Method:** A cross-sectional study was conducted in multiple hospitals across Thi-Qar Province, including Bent Al-Huda and Alshatra hospitals. Data were collected from neonates admitted with respiratory distress symptoms. Key neonatal factors, including age at admission, birth weight, gestational age, and the need for resuscitation, were documented. Maternal factors, such as age, infection status, antenatal care, and labor complications. **Results:** TTN was the most prevalent diagnosis (55%), followed by birth asphyxia (15%) and sepsis (10%). A significant association was found between TTN and cesarean delivery ($p=0.0001$), as well as between maternal infection and neonatal sepsis ($p=0.009$). **Conclusion:** Respiratory distress in full-term neonates is influenced by multiple factors, with TTN linked to cesarean delivery. Early recognition and targeted management are essential to improve outcomes, especially in high-risk cases involving maternal infections and delivery complications.

Introduction

Respiratory distress in full-term neonates during the first week of life is a significant clinical issue; this presentation involves symptoms like tachypnea, nasal flaring, grunting, and retractions. While respiratory distress is typically associated with preterm infants due to their underdeveloped lungs, full-term neonates can also have this problem due to different causes [1]. One common cause is Transient Tachypnea of the Newborn (TTN), which is characterized by a delay in the clearance of fetal lung fluid; this leads to rapid breathing shortly after birth. Newborns delivered via caesarian section often experience TTN, as the mechanical forces of labour aid in the expulsion of fluid from the lungs. Typically, TTN will have a resolution in 24–72 hours with additional care, including oxygen supplements and

monitoring [2]. Meconium Aspiration Syndrome (MAS) is another critical condition that arises when a newborn baby inhales a mixture of meconium and amniotic fluid during or before delivery. This can lead to airway obstruction, inflammation, and infection, all of which lead to respiratory failure. The strategies of management for MAS include respiratory assistance and, in the most severe cases, mechanical ventilation [3]. Infecting causes, such as neonatal pneumonia, can also lead to respiratory failure in full-term infants. Bacterial infections that occur during or after delivery can lead to inflammation of the lungs and a decreased capacity to exchange gases. Effective antibiotic therapy and supportive respiratory care are crucial to dealing with these diseases [4]. Congenital abnormalities, including a diaphragmatic hernia and a congenital heart

More Information

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disease, may lead to respiratory concerns during the neonatal period. These structural irregularities can adversely affect respiratory function, which necessitates surgery and specialized care [5]. Early recognition and effective management of respiratory concerns in full-term newborns is pivotal in avoiding complications like hypoxaemia or acidosis. A comprehensive clinical evaluation, which includes history, a physical exam, and diagnostic imaging, helps identify the primary cause and provide treatment. The improvements in neonatal care have led to increased successes, but the ongoing research and clinical vigilance are still necessary in order to effectively address this complex problem [6]. The aim of the study is to assess the causes, outcomes, and neonatal, maternal, labor, and delivery characteristics of neonates with respiratory distress during the early neonatal period who were admitted to the neonatal care units.

Method

This study on the respiratory distress in full-term newborns during the first week of life in the Thi-Qar Province involved a cross-sectional design that focused on the causes, results, and the neonatal and maternal factors associated with respiratory distress. Midwives conducted the investigation in selected hospitals in the Thi-Qar Province, including Bent Al-Huda Hospital, Alamal Hospital, Alazhar Hospital, Alhabubi Hospital, and Alshatra Hospital, as well as in private hospitals and Suq Alshoukh Hospital, which recorded the highest number of incidents. We gathered data from infants admitted to these units due to respiratory concerns, characterized by symptoms such as tachypnea, nasal flaring, and grunting. Full-term newborns admitted to the hospital within their first week of life participated in the study. Preterm newborns and those with preexisting congenital abnormalities diagnosed prior to birth met the exclusion criteria. We obtained information from both medical records and direct observation, which covered a variety of demographic and clinical parameters. Key neonatal factors included the age of admission, gender, gestational age, birth weight, and the necessity of resuscitation during birth. Other factors associated with the mother were also documented, including maternal age, parity, infection status, history of preterm care, and any complications during childbirth or labor. The investigation used a structured data sheet to maintain consistency in

gathering information about the mother's health status, the type of delivery (caesarean or vaginal), and the place of delivery (public, private, or home). Diagnostic information from chest x-rays and blood tests, when available, supplemented observational data, including the clinical presentation at admission (such as cyanosis, grunting, and tachypnea). The process of data analysis involved describing statistics that summarized the distribution of important variables. Chi-square statistics evaluated the associations between respiratory distress diagnoses (e.g., transient tachypnea of the newborn, birth asphyxia, sepsis) and factors such as delivery method, necessity of resuscitation, and maternal antenatal practices. The level of significance for statistical tests was set at $p < 0.05$ to determine the associations between sociodemographic factors and specific respiratory diagnoses.

Results

Table 1 shows the distribution of patients based on various study variables: **Age:** The majority (63%) are aged ≥ 3 days, while 37% are under 3 days. **Gender:** There is a slight male predominance, with 56% males and 44% females. **Hospital Stay:** A larger percentage of patients (56%) stayed for less than 3 days. **Gestational Age:** Most patients were born at 38 weeks (37%), followed by 39 weeks (31%), with fewer at 37 and 40 weeks. **Weight:** The majority (69%) weighed ≥ 3 kg. **Need for Resuscitation:** Most (85%) required resuscitation at birth. **Type of Delivery:** Delivery was almost evenly split between cesarean section (53%) and vaginal delivery (47%). **Place of Delivery:** Bent Al-Huda Hospital had the highest delivery frequency (43%), followed by private hospitals (32%). **Presentation:** The most common presentations were tachypnea (55%) and grunting (23%). **Chest X-ray Findings:** Most patients (90%) had no abnormal findings. **Complications:** Complications were reported in 29% of cases, with prolonged labor and PROM being the most common. **Maternal Age and Parity:** Most mothers were younger than 30 years (76%) and had less than 3 children (60%). **Antenatal Care:** 65% of mothers had regular antenatal care attendance. **Signs of Infection:** Infections were noted in 53% of mothers. **Education and Occupation:** Most mothers had secondary school education (62%) and were housewives (98%).

Table 1: Distribution of Patients According to Study Variables

variables		frequency	percentage
Age groups (days)	<3	37	37.0
	≥ 3	63	63.0
Gender	<i>Female</i>	44	44.0
	<i>male</i>	56	56.0
Hospital stay	<3	56	56.0

	≥3	44	44.0
Gestational age (weeks)	37	19	19.0
	38	37	37.0
	39	31	31.0
	40	13	13.0
Weight (kg)	<3	31	31.0
	≥3	69	69.0
Need for resuscitation	no	15	15.0
	yes	85	85.0
Types of delivery	CS	53	53.0
	VD	47	47.0
	alamal hospital	1	1.0
	alazhar hospital	1	1.0
Place of delivery	alhabubi hospital	3	3.0
	alshatra hospital	4	4.0
	Bent alhuda hospital	43	43.0
	by midwife in the house	2	2.0
	Private hospital	32	32.0
	suq alshoukh hospital	14	14.0
Presentation	cyanosis	22	22.0
	grunting	23	23.0
	tachypnea	55	55.0
Chest X-ray finding	no	90	90.0
	yes	10	10.0
	meconium liquor	2	2.0
Complications	no	71	71.0
	PPH	3	3.0
	Prolong labor	18	18.0
	PROM	6	6.0
Age of married (years)	<30	76	76.0
	≥30	24	24.0
Parity	<3	60	60.0
	≥3	40	40.0
Medical problems of mother	no	69	69.0
	yes	31	31.0
Antenatal care	irregular	35	35.0
	regular	65	65.0
Signs of infections	No	47	47.0
	yes	53	53.0
APH	no	98	98.0
	yes	2	2.0
Previous RDS	no	85	85.0
	yes	15	15.0
	bachelor degree	5	5.0
Mother education	illiterate	13	13.0
	primary school	20	20.0
	Secondary school	62	62.0
Occupation of mother	Workers	2	2.0
	housewife	98	98.0
Total		100	100

Fig 1 show that 55% of patients have Transient Tachypnea of Newborn, 15% have Birth Asphyxia, 10%

of them have sepsis, 7% of patients have Congenital Heart Diseases and pneumonia.

Fig 1: Distribution of Patients According to Diagnosis

Table 2 examines the relationship between specific diagnoses and various sociodemographic factors: **Age Group:** No significant association with diagnoses, as p-value = 0.7. However, transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) was more common in children aged ≥ 3 days (61.8%). **Hospital Stay:** While not significant (p-value = 0.12), a higher percentage of patients with congenital heart diseases had a hospital stay < 3 days (85.7%). **Gender:** Gender was not significantly associated with diagnosis (p-value = 0.3), though sepsis was more prevalent among males (60%). **Gestational Age:** Gestational age showed no significant link to diagnoses (p-value = 0.12). However, TTN was most common in patients born at 38 weeks (45.5%). **Weight:** Significant association found (p-value = 0.011), with the majority of those diagnosed with birth asphyxia weighing ≥ 3 kg (93.3%). **Mother’s Age:** No significant association with diagnosis (p-value = 0.3), though younger mothers (< 30 years) had children more frequently diagnosed with transient tachypnea (70.9%). **Parity:** Significant association (p-value = 0.001), with birth asphyxia more common in mothers with fewer than 3 previous children (93.3%). **Hospital Place:** Significant (p-value = 0.002), with congenital heart diseases and TTN more prevalent at specific hospitals. **Need for Resuscitation:** Strongly associated (p-value =

0.004), with birth asphyxia and sepsis showing high rates among those needing resuscitation. **Type of Delivery:** Significant association (p-value = 0.0001), with cesarean deliveries linked more to TTN. **Presentation:** No significant association (p-value = 0.18), but tachypnea was more frequent among TTN patients. **X-ray Findings:** No significant association (p-value = 0.1), though 85.5% of TTN patients had normal X-rays. **Delivery Complications:** Significant association (p-value = 0.0001), particularly for sepsis linked with prolonged labor. **Medical Problems in Mother:** Significant (p-value = 0.034), with TTN higher among mothers with medical problems. **Antenatal Care Attendance:** Significant (p-value = 0.026), with irregular attendance associated with congenital defects. **Signs of Infection:** Significant (p-value = 0.009), with pneumonia and sepsis more frequent when infection signs were present in mothers. **Antepartum Hemorrhage (APH):** Significant (p-value = 0.003), with sepsis associated with APH. **Previous Sibling with RDS:** Significant (p-value = 0.044), with transient tachypnea more frequent in families with previous RDS history. **Mother’s Education:** Significant (p-value = 0.007), with congenital heart diseases linked to primary education level. **Mother’s Occupation:** Not significant (p-value = 0.9), as nearly all mothers were housewives.

Table 2: Association between Diagnosis and Sociodemographic Factors

Age Group (day)	Birth Asphyxia	Diagnosis				Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
		Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	
<3	5 (33.3%)	4 (57.1%)	3 (50.0%)	2 (28.6%)	2 (20.0%)	21 (38.2%)
≥3	10 (66.7%)	3 (42.9%)	3 (50.0%)	5 (71.4%)	8 (80.0%)	34 (61.8%)
P-value= 0.7 (not significant)						
Hospital stay (days)	Birth Asphyxia	Diagnosis				Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
		Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	
<3	7 (46.7%)	6 (85.7%)	4 (66.7%)	4 (57.1%)	2 (20.0%)	33 (60.0%)
≥3	8 (53.3%)	1 (14.3%)	2 (33.3%)	3 (42.9%)	8 (80.0%)	22 (40.0%)
P-value= 0.12 (not significant)						
Gender	Birth Asphyxia	Diagnosis				Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
		Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	
female	5 (33.3%)	6 (85.7%)	3 (50.0%)	3 (42.9%)	4 (40.0%)	23 (41.8%)
male	10 (66.7%)	1 (14.3%)	3 (50.0%)	4 (57.1%)	6 (60.0%)	32 (58.2%)
P-value= 0.3 (not significant)						
Gestational age (weeks)	Birth Asphyxia	Diagnosis				Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
		Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	
37	2 (13.3%)	2 (28.6%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (28.6%)	1 (10.0%)	11 (20.0%)
38	2 (13.3%)	4 (57.1%)	3 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (30.0%)	25 (45.5%)
39	9 (60.0%)	1 (14.3%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (28.6%)	4 (40.0%)	13 (23.6%)
40	2 (13.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (42.9%)	2 (20.0%)	6 (10.9%)
P-value= 0.12 (not significant)						
Weight (kg)	Birth Asphyxia	Diagnosis				Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
		Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	
<3	1 (6.7%)	3 (42.9%)	5 (83.3%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (10.0%)	18 (32.7%)
≥3	14 (93.3%)	4 (57.1%)	1 (16.7%)	4 (57.1%)	9 (90.0%)	37 (67.3%)
P-value= 0.011 (significant)						
Mother age (years)	Birth Asphyxia	Diagnosis				Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
		Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	
<30	13 (86.7%)	4 (57.1%)	5 (83.3%)	7 (100.0%)	8 (80.0%)	39 (70.9%)
≥30	2 (13.3%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (20.0%)	16 (29.1%)
P-value= 0.3 (not significant)						
Parity	Birth Asphyxia	Diagnosis				Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
		Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	
<3	14 (93.3%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (83.3%)	6 (85.7%)	6 (60.0%)	29 (52.7%)
≥3	1 (6.7%)	7 (100.0%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (14.3%)	4 (40.0%)	26 (47.3%)
P-value= 0.001 (significant)						
Hospital place	Birth Asphyxia	Diagnosis				Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
		Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	
alamal	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.8%)
alazhar	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.8%)
alhabubi	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (5.5%)
alshatra	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (20.0%)	2 (3.6%)
Bent alhuda	12 (80.0%)	2 (28.6%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (28.6%)	6 (60.0%)	21 (38.2%)
by midwife	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.6%)

Private	3 (20.0%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (14.3%)	2 (20.0%)	22 (40.0%)
suq alshoukh	0 (0.0%)	2 (28.6%)	5 (83.3%)	4 (57.1%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (5.5%)
P-value= 0.002 (significant)						

Table 3 analyzes associations between specific diagnoses and clinical factors, highlighting significant findings:

Need for Resuscitation (p-value = 0.004, significant): **Birth Asphyxia, Pneumonia,** and **Sepsis:** All cases (100%) required resuscitation at birth. **Congenital Heart Diseases** and **Other Congenital Defects:** These required resuscitation in 42.9% and 66.7% of cases, respectively. **Transient Tachypnea of Newborn (TTN):** 83.6% of TTN cases required resuscitation. **Type of Delivery** (p-value = 0.0001, significant): **Cesarean Section (CS):** TTN (76.4%) and congenital defects (50%) were associated with CS, suggesting a higher occurrence of respiratory issues with CS deliveries. **Vaginal Delivery (VD):** Birth Asphyxia (80%) and Sepsis (80%) were more common with VD. **Presentation** (p-value = 0.18, not significant): Diagnoses varied by symptoms, though not significantly: **Tachypnea** was common in TTN (60%) and pneumonia (57.1%). **Cyanosis** was more frequent in congenital heart

diseases (42.9%). **Grunting** was common in birth asphyxia (33.3%) and pneumonia (42.9%). **X-ray Findings** (p-value = 0.1, not significant): **Normal X-rays** were observed in the majority, especially in birth asphyxia, congenital heart diseases, pneumonia, and sepsis, with 100% having no X-ray findings. TTN showed normal X-rays in 85.5% of cases. **Delivery Complications** (p-value = 0.0001, significant): **Prolonged Labor:** Associated with sepsis (50%) and pneumonia (28.6%). **PROM (Premature Rupture of Membranes):** Observed in 26.7% of birth asphyxia cases. **Meconium Liquor:** Linked to pneumonia (28.6%). **Medical Problems in Mother** (p-value = 0.034, significant): **No Medical Problems:** High percentages of birth asphyxia (100%), congenital heart diseases (71.4%), and TTN (56.4%) occurred when mothers had no medical issues. **With Medical Problems:** Associated with TTN (43.6%) and congenital heart diseases (28.6%).

Table 3: Association between Diagnosis and Sociodemographic Factors

	Diagnosis					
	Birth Asphyxia	Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
Need resuscitation						
No	0 (0.0%)	4 (57.1%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	9 (16.4%)
Yes	15 (100.0%)	3 (42.9%)	4 (66.7%)	7 (100.0%)	10(100.0%)	46 (83.6%)
P-value= 0.004 (significant)						
Type of delivery						
CS	3 (20.0%)	2 (28.6%)	3 (50.0%)	1 (14.3%)	2 (20.0%)	42 (76.4%)
VD	12 (80.0%)	5 (71.4%)	3 (50.0%)	6 (85.7%)	8 (80.0%)	13 (23.6%)
P-value= 0.0001 (significant)						
Presentation						
Cyanosis	2 (13.3%)	3 (42.9%)	3 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (40.0%)	10 (18.2%)
Grunting	5 (33.3%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (33.3%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (10.0%)	12 (21.8%)
Tachypnea	8 (53.3%)	4 (57.1%)	1 (16.7%)	4 (57.1%)	5 (50.0%)	33 (60.0%)
P-value= 0.18 (not significant)						
X-ray findings						
No	15 (100.0%)	7 (100.0%)	4 (66.7%)	7 (100.0%)	10 (100.0%)	47 (85.5%)
Yes	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	8 (14.5%)
P-value= 0.1 (not significant)						
Delivery complications						

Meconium	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (28.6%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
No	5 (33.3%)	6 (85.7%)	6 (100.0%)	3 (42.9%)	3 (30.0%)	48 (87.3%)
PPH	1 (6.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (20.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Prolong labor	5 (33.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (28.6%)	5 (50.0%)	6 (10.9%)
PROM	4 (26.7%)	1 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.8%)
P-value= 0.0001 (significant)						
Medical problems for mother	Birth Asphyxia	Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
No	15 (100.0%)	5 (71.4%)	5 (83.3%)	5 (71.4%)	8 (80.0%)	31 (56.4%)
Yes	0 (0.0%)	2 (28.6%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (28.6%)	2 (20.0%)	24 (43.6%)
P-value= 0.034 (significant)						

Table 4 provides a detailed analysis of the associations between various neonatal diagnoses and specific sociodemographic factors, with significant findings highlighted: **ANC (Antenatal Care) Attendance** (p-value = 0.026, significant): **Irregular Attendance: Congenital Heart Diseases:** 28.6% associated with irregular ANC attendance. **Other Congenital Defects:** 66.7% associated with irregular attendance. **Pneumonia** and **Sepsis:** 57.1% and 40%, respectively, associated with irregular attendance. **Regular Attendance: Birth Asphyxia:** 100% associated with regular ANC attendance. **Congenital Heart Diseases:** 71.4% with regular attendance. **TTN:** 61.8% associated with regular ANC attendance. **Mother's Signs of Infection** (p-value = 0.009, significant): **No Infection Signs: Birth Asphyxia:** 80% in mothers without infection signs. **Congenital Heart Diseases** and **TTN:** 42.9% and 49.1%, respectively, with no infection signs. **Infection Signs Present: Pneumonia:** 100% associated with maternal infection signs. **Other Congenital Defects:** 83.3% with infection signs. **Sepsis:** 60% associated with infection signs. **Antepartum Hemorrhage (APH)** (p-value = 0.003,

significant): **No APH:** 100% of cases with birth asphyxia, congenital heart diseases, other congenital defects, pneumonia, and TTN occurred without APH. **Yes to APH: Sepsis:** 20% of cases associated with APH. **Previous Sibling with RDS** (p-value = 0.044, significant): **No Previous Sibling with RDS:** 100% of birth asphyxia, congenital heart diseases, and sepsis cases occurred in the absence of a sibling with RDS. **Yes to Previous Sibling with RDS: TTN:** 25.5% had a family history of RDS. **Mother's Education** (p-value = 0.007, significant): **Secondary Education: Birth Asphyxia:** 100% of cases associated with secondary-educated mothers. **Pneumonia:** 100% with secondary education. **Other Congenital Defects:** 83.3% with secondary education. **Primary Education: Congenital Heart Diseases:** 42.9% of cases associated with primary education. **TTN:** 29.1% associated with primary education. **Mother's Occupation** (p-value = 0.9, not significant): **Housewife:** Most diagnoses across all categories were associated with mothers who were housewives (96.4%). **Workers:** Only 3.6% of TTN cases involved mothers who were employed.

Table 4: Association between Diagnosis and Sociodemographic Factors

	Diagnosis					
ANC attendance	Birth Asphyxia	Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
Irregular	0 (0.0%)	2 (28.6%)	4 (66.7%)	4 (57.1%)	4 (40.0%)	21 (38.2%)
Regular	15 (100.0%)	5 (71.4%)	2 (33.3%)	3 (42.9%)	6 (60.0%)	34 (61.8%)
P-value= 0.026 (significant)						
Mother infections signs	Birth Asphyxia	Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
No	12 (80.0%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (40.0%)	27 (49.1%)
Yes	3 (20.0%)	4 (57.1%)	5 (83.3%)	7 (100.0%)	6 (60.0%)	28 (50.9%)
P-value= 0.009 (significant)						
APH	Birth Asphyxia	Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
No	15 (100.0%)	7 (100.0%)	6 (100.0%)	7 (100.0%)	8 (80.0%)	55 (100.0%)
Yes	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (20.0%)	0 (0.0%)

		P-value= 0.003 (significant)				
Previous sibling with RDS	Birth Asphyxia	Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
No	15 (100.0%)	7 (100.0%)	6 (100.0%)	6 (85.7%)	10(100.0%)	41 (74.5%)
Yes	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	14 (25.5%)
		P-value= 0.044 (significant)				
Mother education	Birth Asphyxia	Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
bachelor	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (20.0%)	3 (5.5%)
Illiterate	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (20.0%)	11 (20.0%)
Primary	0 (0.0%)	3 (42.9%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	16 (29.1%)
Secondary	15 (100.0%)	4 (57.1%)	5 (83.3%)	7 (100.0%)	6 (60.0%)	25 (45.5%)
		P-value= 0.007 (significant)				
Mother occupation	Birth Asphyxia	Congenital Heart Diseases	Other Congenital Defects	Pneumonia	Sepsis	Transient Tachypnea of Newborn
Workers	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.6%)
Housewife	15 (100.0%)	7 (100.0%)	6 (100.0%)	7 (100.0%)	10(100.0%)	53 (96.4%)
		P-value= 0.9 (not significant)				

Discussion

The distribution of demographic data in Table 1 demonstrates a higher frequency of respiratory problems in neonates that are 3 days or more old, with a slight male bias. The majority of the patients required resuscitation, and the most common diagnoses included tachypnea (55%) and grunting (23%). Figure 1 shows that Transient Tachypnea of the Newborn (TTN) was the most common cause of respiratory difficulty (55%), followed by asphyxia during birth (15%) and sepsis (10%). Previous studies have identified TTN as the primary diagnosis of respiratory failure in term newborns, particularly those born via caesarean section, resulting in diminished mechanical forces and a delay in lung fluid clearance [7].

Table 2 shows that sociodemographic factors have a significant association with newborn diagnoses. For instance, we observed a significant association ($p = 0.011$) between birth weight and birth asphyxia, with 93.3% of the affected neonates weighing at least 3 kilograms. This discovery concord with research that suggests that larger birth weights are associated with an increased probability of perinatal complications, including asphyxia [8]. Parity also exhibited a significant association ($p = 0.001$), with the frequency of birth asphyxia increasing in mothers with fewer than three previous children; this may be due to a limited amount of maternal experience or the physiological properties associated with primiparity [9].

The place of delivery was significantly associated with specific respiratory diagnoses ($p = 0.002$); this association suggests that certain hospitals have a higher percentage of TTN and congenital heart disease, which may be due to variations in delivery practices or

the allocation of resources, as discussed by [10]. Neonatal resuscitation significantly correlates with birth asphyxia and sepsis ($p = 0.002$). Additionally, the frequency of caesarean delivery was significantly associated with TTN ($p = 0.0001$), which is in agreement with the findings that newborns born via caesarean have a higher prevalence of TTN due to a lack of effective fluid removal from the lungs, as opposed to vaginal delivery [11].

The analysis in Table 3 showed a significant association between complications during delivery, including prolonged labour and PROM, and sepsis or the lack of birth asphyxia ($p = 0.0001$). This observation concord with previous studies that have reported an increased probability of infection and respiratory issues in newborns born after a long labour or with damaged membranes; these conditions increase the exposure of bacteria [12]. Additionally, neonates that required resuscitation were more likely to have TTN ($p = 0.004$), a finding that was supported by [13], who observed that resuscitated children often have a delayed onset of fluid in the lungs; this could lead to respiratory problems.

Table 4 demonstrates the effects of maternal health on the respiratory outcomes of neonates; the irregular nature of antenatal care is strongly associated with congenital defects ($p = 0.026$). Similar studies demonstrate the importance of consistent antenatal care in recognizing risk factors for congenital abnormalities early on [14]. MateResearchers have found a significant link between maternal infections and the development of neonatal pneumonia and sepsis ($p = 0.009$); this association is consistent with other studies that have highlighted the transmission of

diseases during childbirth as a significant concern [15], antepartum haemorrhage (APH) exhibited a significant association with neonatal sepsis ($p = 0.003$). [16] emphasised this as a significant cause of infection. Also, having a sibling who has had breathing problems in the past was linked to TTN ($p = 0.044$), which could mean that the disease is caused by genetic or environmental factors, as studied by [17]. Overall, the results concur with previous literature, which suggests that sociodemographic factors, delivery methods, and maternal health have a significant impact on the respiratory outcomes of newborns. Early detection and treatment of these risk factors is pivotal in reducing the severity of neonatal respiratory issues and improving the overall results.

Conclusion

To sum up, respiratory distress among full-term neonates is a multifactorial condition that relates to neonatal factors such as gestational age, birth weight, and maternal factors. Our study has brought forth that the most common cause of neonatal respiratory distress is Transient Tachypnea of Newborn (TTN), which is predominantly as a result of caesarean section. There was a significant association of the respiratory outcomes with the need for resuscitation, mode of delivery, and antenatal practices in relation to the study conducted. Timely recognition and appropriate management of these neonates are important for better outcomes, especially in the high-risk cases related to maternal infection and birth complications.

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